

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

STATISTICAL EVALUATION OF PERSONALIZED TRAINING IN SCHOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

This study examines the effects of a personalized training program on the physical performance of seventh-grade students, focusing on improvements in endurance and handball-specific skills. Testing was conducted on two groups of 25 students: the control group (VII C) and the experimental group (VII A). The results showed a significant improvement in the experimental group compared to the control group, as supported by statistical analysis using paired sample t-tests and Wilcoxon tests. The training program proved effective in enhancing the physical and athletic abilities of the experimental group.

Keywords: Paired Sample t-Test, Wilcoxon Test, experimental group, control group, performance, normality test (Shapiro-Wilk)

1. Introduction

Physical education provides more than health benefits—it is also a key context for developing life and sports skills. Handball, as a dynamic and challenging sport, demands not only physical fitness but also quick thinking and precise coordination. Supporting students in achieving these standards requires tailored training and instructional methods.

This research aimed to increase physical endurance and improve handball techniques by applying a personalized training program. Two distinct groups of 25 seventh-grade students participated: the experimental group received custom-designed exercises, while the control group followed the standard physical education curriculum.

2. Testing and methodology description

Testing was carried out at two key moments: at the beginning and end of the school year. This allowed for tracking students' progress following the training period. An intermediate test was planned, but due to unfavorable weather conditions, it was canceled. Despite this, the results obtained from the two conducted evaluations provided essential insights into students' progress. The tests were selected to be relevant and easy to administer, offering a clear view of each participant's abilities.

The testing criteria and control norms were based on:

- The school curriculum for handball initiation in seventh grade;
- The biomotor level of the participating students;
- Methodical instructions for sports training methods and procedures;

- Available material resources (field, balls, equipment, cones).

The control tests used were:

- 800 m endurance run: to assess students' endurance capacity;
- Passing in pairs while moving over a 10 m distance: to evaluate coordination and teamwork skills;
- Shuttle drill with change to the opposite line: to assess speed, agility, and change-of-direction skills.

This study aims to identify how personalized training programs can influence students' progress in both physical endurance and technical handball skills. By selecting relevant and practical methods, the research seeks not only to evaluate student performance but also to highlight the specific needs of each group.

Particular attention was paid to the experimental group, where specialized methods and methodological adaptations were expected to have a more significant impact. The research focuses on analyzing progress achieved during the intervention and the extent to which periodic strategy adjustments contribute to the success of educational programs.

Through this approach, the paper aims to offer a clear perspective on the applicability of training methods in modern physical education.

3. Methodological details and performance improvement activities [1]

3.1. The 800 m endurance run

Students began running at an audible signal, and each individual's time was recorded in Table 1. The performance improvement exercises used for the experimental group included:

- Varied pace running on flat terrain: 300 m at tempo 2/4 followed by 100 m at tempo 3/4;

- Uniform pace running on flat terrain: continuous 800 m run;
- Gradual workload increase: endurance running up to 1000 m;
- Repeated sprints: counterattack-style sprints ending with goal throws;
- Sprint passes: sprints with passing between two players across a handball court length;
- Series of short sprints: 7–8 m repeated sprints.

3.2. Test for passing in two from a distance of 10 m

Students worked in pairs and passed the ball over a 10-meter distance for one minute, counting successful passes.

Improvement exercises used in the experimental group:

- passing between two players with gradually increasing distance;
- medicine ball throws (1 kg) over distance;
- passing while moving using a 1 kg medicine ball;
- preparatory games involving the 1 kg medicine ball.

3.3. Test of Simplified shuttle drill with transition to the opposite end of the line

Two groups of 12 students were formed, each group splitting into two parallel lines of six, with a 7-meter distance between the first players.

The performance-enhancing exercises the experimental group worked with were as follows:

- Simple shuttle drill with progressive volume increase: more repetitions and increased distance between players;
- Shuttle drill using 1 kg medicine balls instead of handball.

Additional exercises aimed at improving handball-specific endurance:

- Movement in fundamental position: five 30-second rounds of continuous movement;
- 7 vs. 7 school game played on two goals;
- Handball training game “Who holds the ball longer”;
- Two-gates game with man-to-man defense on half court.
- Two-gates game: 2 halves of 10 minutes each.

Fig.1. Test of Simplified shuttle drill with transition to the opposite end of the line

The expected outcomes from the above exercises consists of:

1. Improvement in physical performance: students in the experimental group were expected to show significant gains at the final tests due to the specific and additional training;
2. Enhanced endurance and technical handball skills from the varied, targeted exercises.

4. Results and interpretations

To evaluate the effectiveness of the training program, tests were conducted at the beginning and end of the school year, and the results from both groups were compared.

The performance results of the 25 students in the experimental group (EG) and 25 students in the control group (CG), both at the initial testing (IT) and the final testing (FT) for the 800 m endurance run, are summarized in Table 1, forming the basis for statistical analysis.

Table 1.

Results obtained by students in both groups in both tests, in the 800 m endurance running event

	A	B	C	D	E
	No. crt.	Endurance running 800 m IT-E.G.	Endurance running 800 m IT-C.G.	Endurance running 800 m FT-E.G.	Endurance running 800 m FT-C.G.
1					
2	1	5,40	3,55	5,04	3,52
3	2	3,24	4,36	3,17	4,33
4	3	5,49	3,58	5,40	4,02
5	4	5,49	6,05	5,28	6,01
6	5	5,58	3,54	5,25	3,46
7	6	4,30	3,55	4,11	3,37
8	7	5,04	3,48	4,34	3,41
9	8	3,52	6,06	3,24	5,58
10	9	5,42	4,15	5,30	5,23
11	10	3,27	5,51	3,13	5,48
12	11	3,50	5,06	3,33	4,51
13	12	5,51	3,10	5,31	3,15
14	13	3,47	4,32	3,26	4,32
15	14	3,48	3,51	3,30	3,37
16	15	3,05	5,01	3,01	5,02
17	16	3,20	5,07	3,18	5,06
18	17	3,36	3,00	3,25	2,54
19	18	4,22	5,22	4,09	5,12
20	19	5,40	4,36	5,23	4,33
21	20	4,08	6,07	3,55	5,46
22	21	4,18	5,03	3,28	4,28
23	22	5,20	3,43	4,32	3,48
24	23	5,03	3,52	4,51	3,51
25	24	5,31	4,03	5,01	3,39
26	25	5,40	4,13	5,07	4,02

The results from Table 1 were analyzed using the Paired Sample t-Test, with outcomes displayed in Figures 1a and 1b.

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means			t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	Endurance running 800 m IT-E.G.	Endurance running 800 m FT-E.G.		Endurance running 800 m IT-C.G.	Endurance running 800 m FT-C.G.
Mean	4,4456	4,1584	Mean	4,3476	4,2388
Variance	0,904967333	0,818472333	Variance	0,912460667	0,851011
Observations	25	25	Observations	25	25
Pearson Correlation	0,967083865		Pearson Correlation	0,923802776	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0		Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	24		df	24	
t Stat	5,920487608		t Stat	1,478604837	
P(T<=t) one-tail	2,0722E-06		P(T<=t) one-tail	0,076125868	
t Critical one-tail	1,71088208		t Critical one-tail	1,71088208	
P(T<=t) two-tail	4,1444E-06		P(T<=t) two-tail	0,152251737	
t Critical two-tail	2,063898562		t Critical two-tail	2,063898562	

a) Experimental group solution b) Control group solution

Figure 2. Solution provided by the Jamovi program

Figure 1a shows an improvement of 0.2872 minutes in average running time for the experimental group, while Figure 1b reveals a 0.1088 minutes improvement for the control group. The variance suggests homogeneity in the response to training of students in both classes, as performance differences are relatively stable between initial and final tests. Pearson correlation values (0.967 and 0.923) indicate strong correlations between individual performances in the two test sessions.

In the E.G. the t-stat value of 5.920487608 is much higher than the critical values, namely: 1.71088208 for one-tail and 2.063898562 for two-tail, respectively, and the P-value is well below 0.05, being even below 0.001, which indicates that the observed improvement is highly statistically significant, so the interventions and exercises applied to the experimental class had a significant positive effect on the performance in the 800 m running test. The Bayes factor and the Wilcoxon test (fig.2) also confirm this significant difference. The result of the Wilcoxon test (Wilcoxon W = 325, $p < 0.001$) confirms the results of the t-test, showing that the difference between the experimental group data sets at baseline and final testing is significant even when the

data are not assumed to follow a normal distribution. This use of the Wilcoxon test, together with the t-test, provides a complete and robust picture of the results, confirming that the applied training program had a significant impact on the physical performance of the students in the experimental group.

In C.G. the t-stat value of 1.478604837 is lower than the critical values (for both one-tail and two-tail), and the P-value is greater than 0.05, indicating that the observed improvement is not statistically significant, so in the control group, the applied exercises did not have a significant effect on performance compared to the experimental class. Unlike the t-test which did not show a significant difference, the Wilcoxon test (fig.2) shows that there is a significant difference ($p = 0.011$). This suggests that although the data do not meet the assumption of normality, there is still a significant difference between the two data sets when using the non-parametric Wilcoxon test, as this test is more sensitive to non-normal data. However, the statistical significance is smaller and, in the overall context of the results, suggests that the improvements in the control group are not as pronounced or relevant as in the experimental group.

Table 2.

The results of the two-pass away - experimental group

No. crt.	A	B	C		D
			Pass in two on the move E.G.		
		First and last name	I.T.	F.T.	
1					
2					
3	1	A.T - A.E	24	27	
4	2	B.A - B.T	22	25	
5	3	C.E - C.M	22	25	
6	4	C.R - D.C	27	31	
7	5	D.A - K.A	24	26	
8	6	L.B - O.S	25	27	
9	7	P.R - R.P	25	30	
10	8	R.A - R.A	27	32	
11	9	S.A - S.C	24	30	
12	10	S.M - S.L	22	25	
13	11	T.M.A - T.C	23	26	
14	12	V.A - V.D	24	28	

		Statistic	df	p	
A	B	Student's t	-10.0	11.0	<.001
		Wilcoxon W	0.00		0.002

Note. H₀: $\mu_{\text{Measure 1}} - \mu_{\text{Measure 2}} = 0$

		W	p
A	- B	0.903	0.172

Note. A low p-value suggests a violation of the assumption of normality

	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
A	12	24.1	24.0	1.73	0.499
B	12	27.7	27.0	2.50	0.721

Figure 3. Results of the t-test and Wilcoxon t-test for the experimental group

Results (fig.3) suggest that the interventions and exercises applied to the experimental class had a significant effect on the average improvement in the number of passes completed per pair per minute (3.6 passes). The statistical results indicate that this improvement is

not coincidental, but reflects a real change in performance, confirmed by both t-test and Wilcoxon test, and can be attributed to the training or other factors that influenced the final testing, demonstrating the effectiveness of the intervention applied between the two tests.

Table 3

Results of the away two-a-side passing test - control group

No. crt.	F	G	H		I
			Pass in two on the move C.G.		
		First and last name	I.T.	F.T.	
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					
11					
12					
1		AA - B.O	23	25	
2		B.D.V - C.G.A.O	22	22	
3		C.E - C.M	22	23	
4		C.R - D.D	24	26	
5		F.R - G.C	24	26	
6		I.B.M - I.C	23	22	
7		M.C - P.R	25	25	
8		P.D - P.R	24	27	
9		P.S - S.E	27	30	
10		S.V - T.N.A	22	25	
11		V.A.C - V.A	23	24	
12		V.M - V.P	24	26	

Paired Samples T-Test								
Paired Samples T-Test								
			Statistic	±%	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference
A	B	Student's t	-3.95		11.0	0.002	-1.50	0.379
		Bayes factor ₁₀	20.2	3.66e-8				
		Wilcoxon W	2.00*			0.010	-2.00	0.379
Note. H ₀ : Measure 1 - Measure 2 = 0 * 2 pair(s) of values were tied								
Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk)								
			W	p				
A	-	B	0.903	0.174				
Note. A low p-value suggests a violation of the assumption of normality								
Descriptives								
	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE			
A	12	23.6	23.5	1.44	0.417			
B	12	25.1	25.0	2.23	0.645			

Figure 4. Results of the t-test and Wilcoxon t-test for the control group

The results (Fig. 4) indicate that although the mean improvement in the control class (1.5 passes) is not as large as in the experimental class (3.6 passes), it is still statistically significant.

The assumption of normality was not violated, and this can be observed from the normality test (Shapiro-Wilk). Regarding the interpretation of the result obtained after applying the paired samples t-test, we have $t=-3.95$ and $p=0.002$, i.e. the dataset representing the final test has a higher value than the dataset corresponding to the initial test, which indicates a significant improvement in performance. The Wilcoxon test confirms the significant difference between the two tests in the control group.

From the beginning to the end of the study, the results showed a significant increase in student performance. Using statistical methods, such as t-test and Wilcoxon, it was confirmed that this change is not random. The data was carefully analyzed for validity and the results were conclusive.

This progress is not surprising, due to the intervention between the two tests, well thought out exercises, which had a positive effect on student performance.

Tables 4 and 5 present the data obtained from the timing of the completion time of the suveic test by the experienced and control groups respectively. In Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 are given the results of the tests carried out on each group, both with the Analysis Tool Pak module of the Microsoft Excel program and with the Jamovi program.

Table 4.

The results of the Suveic sample - experimental group

1	A		B		C		D	
	No. crt.	First and last name	Simple Suveica		I.T. (sec.)	F.T. (sec.)		
2								
3	1	A.T	30,12	26,47				
4	2	A.E						
5	3	B.A						
6	4	B.T						
7	5	C.E						
8	6	C.M						
9	7	C.R						
10	8	D.C						
11	9	D.A						
12	10	K.A						
13	11	L.B						
14	12	O.S						
15	1	P.R	30,38	27,02				
16	2	R.P						
17	3	R.A						
18	4	R.A						
19	5	S.A						
20	6	S.C						
21	7	S.M						
22	8	S.L						
23	9	T.M.A						
24	10	T.C						
25	11	V.A						
26	12	V.D						

Figure 5. Results of t-tests and Wilcoxon t-tests for the experimental group (Excel and Jamovi)

The results (Fig. 5) indicate that the observed improvement in execution time for the suveic in the experimental class is statistically significant. The mean difference of 3.505 seconds is significant, suggesting that the interventions applied had a positive effect on the students' performance on this test.

The t-test returned a value of 24.2 and a p-value of 0.026, suggesting a statistically significant difference between the two tests for the experimental group.

The Wilcoxon test showed no significant difference (p-value = 0.500). This suggests that when normality is not assumed, differences between measurements are not strong enough to be considered statistically significant.

However, it should be noted that the very small number of observations (only 2) may affect the validity of the conclusions and the generalizability of the results. A more robust conclusion would require a larger number of observations.

Table 5.

Results of the suveic test - control group

No. crt.	First and last name	Simple Suveica	
		I.T. (sec.)	F.T. (sec.)
		1	A.A
2	B.O		
3	B.D.V		
4	C.G.A.O		
5	C.E		
6	C.M		
7	C.R		
8	D.D		
9	F.R		
10	G.C		
11	I.B.M		
12	I.C		
1	M.C	30,17	29,03
2	P.R		
3	P.D		
4	P.R		
5	P.S		
6	S.E		
7	S.V		
8	T.N.A		
9	V.A.C		
10	V.A		
11	V.M		
12	V.P		

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
Simple Suveica C.G.		
	I.T. (sec.)	F.T. (sec.)
Mean	30,25	29,25
Variance	0,0128	0,0968
Observations	2	2
Pearson Correlation	1	
Hypothesized Mean Diffe	0	
df	1	
t Stat	7,142857143	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0,044275613	
t Critical one-tail	6,313751515	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0,088551227	
t Critical two-tail	12,70620474	

Paired Samples T-Test						
Paired Samples T-Test						
		Statistic	±%	df	p	
A	B	Student's t	7.14		1.00	0.089
		Bayes factor ₁₀	1.94	4.59e-4		
		Wilcoxon W	3.00			0.500

Figure 6. Results of t-tests and Wilcoxon t-tests for the control group

The results (Fig. 6) indicate that the observed improvement in execution time for the control class of suveic is statistically significant for a unidirectional test, but not for a bidirectional test. The mean difference of 1 second suggests an improvement, but there is the same problem as for the experimental group, i.e. the small number of observations (only 2) which may affect the validity of the conclusions and the generalizability of the results. The t-test results indicate a possible difference between measurements, but this difference is not statistically significant ($p = 0.089$). The Bayes factor₁₁₀ also suggests weak evidence in favor of the existence of a difference, but the Wilcoxon test showed no significant difference.

Conclusions

The study demonstrates that the personalized training program applied to the experimental group was effective in significantly improving physical performance, particularly in the 800-meter endurance run. The results show that in both cases there is a significant difference between the compared data sets, but the impact of the intervention seems to be more pronounced in the experimental group (baseline vs. final testing) than in the control group. In conclusion, the differentiated approach applied to the experimental group led to better results than the conventional methods used in the control group.

For the 10-meter moving pass in two test, the experimental group showed a significant improvement in performance (mean increase of 3.6 passes) compared to the control group (mean increase of 1.5 passes). Also, for the experimental group, the t-test and Wilcoxon test show that the observed differences are statistically significant, highlighting the effectiveness of the training program, but for the control group, although the improvement was statistically significant, the magnitude of this improvement was considerably smaller than that observed for the experimental group. The difference in improvement between the two groups suggests that the training program applied to the experimental group was not only effective, but also resulted in significantly greater progress in specific game skills compared to the standard approach or no intervention in the control group.

On the last test, the experimental group showed a statistically significant improvement in performance, confirmed by the t-test, compared to the control group, suggesting that the standard methods or lack of intervention did not have a sufficient impact on performance.

All these findings reflect the fact that the specific intervention applied to the experimental group led to superior results in all three control samples compared to the traditional or non-interventionist method in the control group.

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